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Evaluation & Impact Assessment
**SCIENTOMETRICS, PATENTS
AND SPIN-OFFS**

<p>MAA Scenario</p> <p>EVALUATION & IMPACT ASSESSMENT</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>Interim and ex-post.</p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>Any.</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>High, advanced quantitative and IT skills needed.</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>Depends on the project size and data volume.</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>PC and software access, data collection costs if not available.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tool # 34, 35, 36.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC

Purpose

Scientometrics, patents and spinoffs are used to:

- Assess the scientific performance of the projects
- Identify innovation outputs
- Support academic rankings and scientific careers.

Background and Logic

This evaluation field is particularly focused on measuring scientific performance. Evaluation methods rely on qualitative, quantitative and computational (using advanced computer aid) approaches. In quantitative terms, most attention is paid to data collection, which depicts the impacts of scientific publications. Common Scientometric indicators include:

Impact Factor (IF)

The impact factor (IF) or journal impact factor (JIF) of an academic journal enables measurement with yearly average number of citations in relation with the recently published articles in a given scientific journal. This factor helps to estimate the relative importance of the scientific outputs. This measurement could be applied for the assessment of results of agricultural innovation projects, where scientific actors are directly involved in co-creation for innovation. This indicator helps with the comparison of performances between projects, organisations, individual researchers and science fields.

Science Citation Index (SCI)

This is a trademarked index owned by Clarivate Analytics. It was originally developed by the Institute of Scientific Information in 1964. A large number of journals is covered throughout dozens of disciplines. The reference journals are the world leaders in science and technology.

Author-level metrics

This is a broad category, which measures scientific performance of the individuals. Some of the popular indicators include h-index, author-level 'Eigenfaktor', 'erdős number', 'i10-index' and RG Score. Various critics are associated with these metrics, such as inaccurate influencing the scores through self-citations.

Acknowledgement Index

The measurement focuses on indexing and analyzing acknowledgments in the scientific literature. The index measures influence on the scientific work that are institutional and economic. Moreover, it considers the informal influences that are connected to individuals. The metric provides an analytical approach for several components. The index is supported by the automated digital library CiteSeerX. Google Scholar and Microsoft Academic Search. The library allows for automated data extraction and crawling (a bot, script, or software grabs content and links from a website), among others.

Patents

This measurement is supportive to analysis of the project outputs in terms of market expansion. Patents concern rights to use a given inventions that are legally registered and protected. An economic impact is typically associated with the patent but can be enabled or constrained due to various circumstances. Patent procedures vary between countries, even within the EC. Patents are also widely applied in the international comparative analyses of the R&I performance. At the global level, useful search engines are powered by the Google Patents and WIPO Patents (World Intellectual Property Organization).

Spin-offs

Creation of spin-offs is intended to support transformation of the technological innovations from the scientific context towards other application domains. This is a part of the exploitation process, typically oriented on further development and commercialization of the R&I outputs. Several types of spin-offs can be distinguished, e.g., companies with equity investment from a research institution, companies with a technology license from a public research entity, companies founded by a researcher affiliated with a public research institution or companies created directly by the research entity.

Source: www.ilovephd.com

